

Enhanced Access to Safe Water Through Community Partnerships: A Case of Nkoowe, Wakiso District

Moureen Bulakya¹, Mark D. Walugembe², Norah Kiwabudde³, Bruce Musinguzi⁴, Job Matovu⁵

^{1,2,3,4,5}Africa Renewal University - Buloba, Uganda

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Corresponding Author:

Moureen Bulakya

ABSTRACT

The availability of clean and safe water is an ongoing challenge for peri-urban populations in Uganda, with Nkoowe in Wakiso District being a notable example. In spite of efforts from governmental bodies and Non-Governmental Organisations, numerous inhabitants still depend on unreliable water sources, resulting in health hazards and socio-economic difficulties. This article conducts a review of the current literature and reports to analyse the tangible obstacles to water access in Nkoowe, underscoring the effects on public health, economic activities and overall development. Suggestions for community-oriented strategies and enhancements in policy are presented to facilitate sustainable access to safe water.

KEYWORDS: Clean water, access to water, Nkoowe, Wakiso District, public health, water infrastructure.

1. INTRODUCTION

Water is critical for human life, health and development. Despite this, many peri-urban areas in Uganda still face persistent challenges in access to clean and safe water. Nkoowe in Wakiso District is just the kind of area where the communities use unprotected wells, springs and streams repeatedly. Inaccessible or inadequate access increases the risk of waterborne diseases, reduces productivity and hinders social development. This article synthesises recent literature on the practical issues surrounding access to water in Nkoowe and explores possible interventions for increasing sustainable access to water.

2. BACKGROUND

Water scarcity and pollution are widespread across sub-Saharan Africa. In Uganda, population growth, urbanisation and weak infrastructure have deepened the problem, particularly in peri-urban areas like Nkoowe. Over the last decade, government reports (Ministry of Water and Environment (Uganda), 2022) show that more than 35% of rural water sources are non-functional due to poor maintenance and low community participation.

In Nkoowe, residents depend largely on boreholes, well-sinking (the manual process of digging shallow wells), and nearby streams for daily water needs. However, many of these sources lack reliability i.e. they break down frequently, experience seasonal drying and poor maintenance makes them unsustainable. Furthermore, water drawn from shallow wells and open streams is often contaminated with faecal

matter, pesticides, and other pollutants, posing severe health risks such as diarrhoea, typhoid, cholera, and skin infections (Bain et al., 2014; WHO, 2023; Howard et al., 2021; Clasen et al., 2015). Research shows that contaminated water sources contribute significantly to diarrhoeal diseases among children under five (Bain et al., 2014; Howard et al., 2021).

Socio-economic factors such as a low/unstable income, low education levels and issues like not being able to own land also makes the challenge worse. Many households in Nkoowe have low and unstable incomes, limiting their ability to pay for water user fees or contribute to the maintenance of communal sources. Weak community structures and limited leadership reduce accountability for water source management. Low awareness of hygiene and water safety practices further restricts access to safe drinking water (Mugumya & Kayiso, 2019).

Within this context, NGOs such as *Show Mercy International* have intervened through community-based well-digging projects, hygiene training, and local empowerment initiatives (Kanyesigye et al., 2020). Their work demonstrates how NGO-community partnerships can help fill gaps left by public systems, improving sustainability and ownership.

3. RESEARCH QUESTIONS

This study seeks to explore how NGO-community partnerships can be used as a strategic approach to improve access to safe water in Nkoowe, Wakiso District.

3.1 Main Research Question

How can NGO–community partnerships be used in a practical, effective way as a sustainable strategy to increase access to safe water in Nkoowe, Wakiso District?

3.2 Specific Research Questions

1. What are the main challenges affecting access to clean and safe water in Nkoowe?
2. What role have NGOs (such as Show Mercy International) played in improving water access and management in peri-urban Uganda?
3. What partnership models have proven effective in promoting sustainability in the Ugandan water sector?
4. How can NGOs be supported to provide a sustainable solution for increasing access to safe water in Nkoowe?

4. RELATED WORKS

Existing studies in sub-Saharan Africa highlight that access to clean water depends on local governance, financing and community participation. Hope et al. (2020) found that financial accountability and stakeholder collaboration significantly influence rural water sustainability. Kanyesigye et al. (2020) demonstrated that NGO-led projects, when community-driven, show higher long-term functionality. In Uganda, Mugumya & Kayiso (2019) observed that poor maintenance and limited funding lead to frequent breakdowns of boreholes and wells.

The role of NGOs has become increasingly critical, particularly in regions where public infrastructure is inadequate. Oyo et al. (2022) reported that collaborative efforts between local governments and NGOs improved efficiency and community satisfaction in rural water schemes. However, research on how such models can be applied to specific localities like Nkoowe remains limited and this creates an opportunity for this study to fill that contextual gap.

5. METHODOLOGY

This study will employ a qualitative, descriptive research design based solely on secondary data. Peer-reviewed journal articles, government documents and NGO reports were reviewed thematically to identify recurring challenges and potential solutions related to safe water access in Uganda. The analysis will focus on:

1. Institutional mechanisms supporting water access
2. The role of NGOs and community partnerships
3. Practical models applicable to Nkoowe.

6. FINDINGS

The review indicates that water access in Nkoowe is hindered by inadequate infrastructure, weak maintenance systems and low financial commitment at community level. However, literature consistently shows that projects integrating local participation achieve higher success rates. NGO–community

partnerships, such as those implemented by *Show Mercy International*, have provided practical evidence that when communities contribute labour, land, or maintenance fees, project ownership and sustainability improve.

Challenges remain in ensuring water quality monitoring, maintaining borehole functionality, and aligning NGO activities with local government plans. Many NGO projects also rely on donor funding and limiting long-term scalability. Nonetheless, community-based partnerships emerge as a viable path toward sustainable water access in Nkoowe and similar peri-urban areas.

7. FUTURE WORKS

Future studies should investigate financial sustainability models for community water projects, including micro-financing and revolving maintenance funds. Hands-on work involving local households, government officials, and NGOs could deepen understanding of user behaviour and maintenance challenges. There is also scope for integrating digital monitoring systems such as mobile-based reporting tools to track borehole functionality and improve accountability across stakeholders.

8. CONCLUSIONS

This study concludes that NGO–community partnerships provide an effective framework for increasing access to safe water in areas like Nkoowe. By combining community ownership with NGO expertise and resources, such collaborations address both physical and behavioural barriers to clean water access. The case of Nkoowe demonstrates that targeted well-digging and training initiatives can significantly reduce dependence on unsafe water sources. Moving forward, enhanced coordination with public authorities, consistent funding and community empowerment will be key to ensuring long-term sustainability.

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Computing from Uganda Christian University, Mukono. Dr. Matovu is a Lecturer and Researcher in the Department of Information Technology at Africa Renewal University. He specializes in Payment Information Technology Security, particularly authentication systems, and his research spans cybersecurity, electronic commerce, business information systems, ICT policy and strategy, ICT for development (ICT4D), mobile and wireless technologies, artificial intelligence and database management systems.

Bibliographical Notes

Moureen Bulakya holds a bachelor’s degree in Information Technology from YMCA, Wandegaya, and is currently pursuing a master’s degree in Organisational Leadership at Africa Renewal University, Buloba. She serves as the Director of Finance and Administration at Show Mercy International, bringing extensive experience in organisational management and project oversight. Her professional and research interests focus on sustainable development, with particular attention to practical strategies for improving access to safe water and advancing the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals, including ending poverty.

Dr. Mark D. Walugembe, holds a Doctoral Degree in Biblical Studies from Midwest bible college US, a Masters of arts in Leadership from Pan African University in Kenya and a bachelor’s of science with education from Makerere university.

Norah Kiwabudde, holds a bachelor’s of Science with education from Kyambogo University and a Masters of Business Administration in Finance and Accounting from Africa Renewal University. She is currently the Head of Business department at Africa Renewal University, Buloba.

Mr. Bruce Musinguzi holds a bachelor’s degree in computer science and a masters in business administration, he currently serves as the IT operations and systems administrator at Africa Renewal University, Buloba.

Job Matovu, PhD, obtained his doctorate in Information Technology from Makerere University, following a Master’s in Information Technology and a Bachelor’s in Business